

Comparison of in-vitro immunomodulatory capacity between large and small apoptotic bodies from human bone marrow mesenchymal stromal cells

Jiemin Wang^{a,b}, Seyedmohammad Moosavizadeh^{a,b}, Manon Jammes^a, Abbas Tabasi^a,
Trung Bach^a, Aideen E. Ryan^{a,b,c,*}, Thomas Ritter^{a,b,**}

^a Regenerative Medicine Institute, School of Medicine, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

^b CURAM Centre for Research in Medical Devices, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

^c Discipline of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, School of Medicine, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mesenchymal stromal cell (MSC) apoptosis is essential for their therapeutic effects, including immunomodulation. Previous studies have shown that MSC-derived apoptotic bodies (ApoBDs) also possess immunomodulatory properties. However, compared to small extracellular vesicles, the preparation, characterization, and biological properties of ApoBDs remain underexplored.

Results: ApoBDs were isolated from the conditioned medium of staurosporine-induced apoptotic human MSCs and categorized into large (~700 nm) and small (~500 nm) groups. Both types expressed CD90, CD44, and CD73, with low levels of PD-L1, CD11b, and HLA-DR, mirroring their parental MSCs. Functional assays revealed that both ApoBDs inhibited allogeneic T-cell proliferation, with large ApoBDs demonstrating superior efficacy. In macrophage co-culture experiments, both ApoBDs polarized M1 macrophages toward an M2-like phenotype, with large ApoBDs more effectively upregulating CD163 expression. Additionally, both ApoBDs suppressed the proliferation of murine primary T cells. Furthermore, large ApoBDs exhibited enhanced macrophage uptake, as confirmed by flow cytometry and immunocytochemistry. Importantly, no cytotoxicity was observed for either ApoBD type following staurosporine treatment.

Conclusions: Staurosporine-induced ApoBDs are non-cytotoxic and exhibit significant immunomodulatory potential in vitro. Large ApoBDs are more effective than small ApoBDs in T-cell suppression and M2 macrophage polarization, suggesting their potential as an alternative to MSC-based therapies in future studies.

List of abbreviations

Apoptotic bodies	ApoBDs
extracellular vesicles	EVs
the International Society for Extracellular Vesicles	ISEV
large apoptotic bodies	L-ApoBDs
mesenchymal stromal cells	MSCs
peripheral blood mononuclear cells	PBMCs
small apoptotic bodies	S-ApoBDs

1. Introduction

Mesenchymal stromal cells (MSCs) have been recognized as potent immunomodulatory [1,2] and anti-inflammatory [3–5] agents, in conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis, type 1 diabetes and uveitis. Regarding the therapeutic mechanisms of MSCs, studies have shown that they inhibit T cell proliferation [6] and increase the frequency of regulatory T cells (Tregs) [7,8]. However, challenges such as limited efficacy [9] and immunogenicity problems [10–13] following MSC administration remain significant hurdles that currently hinder their broader therapeutic application.

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) exhibit biological properties similar to

* Corresponding author at: Discipline of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, School of Medicine, University of Galway, Ireland.

** Corresponding author at: Regenerative Medicine Institute, School of Medicine, Biomedical Sciences, University of Galway, Newcastle Road, Ireland.

E-mail addresses: aideen.ryan@universityofgalway.ie (A.E. Ryan), thomas.ritter@universityofgalway.ie (T. Ritter).

those of their parental cells [14–16]. Based on their biogenesis, EVs can be categorized into exosomes, ectosomes/microvesicles, or apoptotic bodies (ApoBDs). Exosomes are released from live cells when multi-vesicular bodies fuse with the cell membrane [17–19]. In contrast, ApoBDs are produced by apoptotic cells, characterized by chromatin condensation, membrane blebbing, and the disintegration of cellular contents into distinct membrane-enclosed vesicles.

Recent studies have confirmed that ApoBDs possess therapeutic effects similar to those of their parental non-apoptotic cells [20–23] based on comparable proteomic [23] and transcriptional [22] signatures. Importantly, it has been reported that MSCs undergo apoptosis *in vivo* following transplantation [24] which was required for their therapeutic function [25]. This raises the intriguing possibility that ApoBDs generated *in vivo* could replace live MSC delivery.

Theoretically, ApoBD therapy (cell-free therapy) has low immunogenicity [26–28] and offers advantages in terms of storage and transportation compared to live cells. Our previous study demonstrated that human bone marrow MSC-derived ApoBDs can inhibit allogeneic T cell proliferation, reduce pro-inflammatory cytokines secreted by M1 macrophages, and induce a greater number of Tregs [29]. Furthermore, MSC-derived ApoBDs have proven effective in models of wound healing [30] and myocardial infarction [31].

Currently, the methods for inducing apoptosis to produce ApoBDs vary. The most commonly used method is staurosporine [25,31,32], which is known for its high and stable induction efficiency. However, the cytotoxicity of staurosporine has been widely discussed, as residual staurosporine may remain in the ApoBD samples and lead to cell dysfunction. Another method involves using ultraviolet (UV) light to induce apoptotic cells [33,34]. Although the ApoBDs produced by this method are non-cytotoxic, the optimal intensity and duration for achieving maximum yield have yet to be optimized and confirmed. A third feasible method is the use of high concentrations of other compounds, such as dexamethasone [35,36]. However, this approach is less popular due to uncertainty regarding the optimal concentration required for effective induction. Lastly, while hypoxia can induce cell apoptosis [37,38], there have been no reports of hypoxia-induced apoptotic bodies. In this study, we adopted the most widely used apoptotic agent, staurosporine, to induce apoptotic MSCs.

The study of subtypes of EVs is currently a popular field, as this type of research can achieve homogenization of EVs, clarify the components and increase stability between EV batches. For example, early in 2017, it was reported that adipocyte-derived large and small EVs were distinct in some expressions of lipid and protein. These contributed to the EV subtype identification [39]. The example above is utilizing size as the distinguished principle. Another popular example is protein composition. Karimi et al. isolated different subpopulations of human serum EVs based on the protein antigen/antibody affinity. They found a high number of CD9+ EVs and a small number of CD63+/CD81+ [40]. Different surface markers may represent different phenotypes and sources of EV. While research on EV subtypes is highly active and rapidly progressing, studies on ApoBD subtypes remain comparatively limited and underexplored.

In terms of ApoBD preparation, there are no very strict criteria like for EVs, as published by International Society of Extracellular Vesicles (ISEV) [41]. In recently published literature, centrifugation was usually used to isolate the ApoBDs, but there was no accepted and standardized method (centrifugation condition). Some researchers isolated the supernatant in 3000 g for 20–30 min [42–44], while others did in 16,000 g [30,45,46]. According to their characterization and our previous study, we speculated that 3000 g would isolate large vesicles and 16,000 g would isolate small vesicles. The size of ApoBDs was regarded as the principle method to distinguish the two subpopulations in this study.

Herein, we prepared two categories of ApoBDs deriving from staurosporine-induced apoptotic human bone marrow MSCs. The two categories of ApoBDs, which were distinct in size, were isolated by different centrifugation conditions. The sizes of the two types of ApoBDs

were quantified using a Malvern Zeta Potential Analyzer, and the size difference was further confirmed by flow cytometry. We found both types of ApoBDs are non-cytotoxic and exhibit immunomodulatory potential *in vitro*. Compared with small ApoBDs, large ApoBDs are more efficient in inhibiting human and mouse T-cell proliferation and human M2-macrophage polarization. ApoBDs could be useful in future studies replacing cell therapies with MSCs.

2. Methods

2.1. Isolation, culture, and characterization of MSC from human bone marrow

The details of this section can be found in the Supplementary Materials.

2.2. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) isolation and culture

Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated by density-gradient centrifugation as described in our previous study [29]. The PBMCs were obtained from whole blood samples, with written informed consent from four healthy volunteers (Clinical Research Ethics Committee, Galway University Hospital). PBMCs were cultured in RPMI-1640 medium (BioSciences, Dublin, Ireland) supplemented with 1 % penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland) and 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland).

2.3. Macrophage-like THP-1 cell culture

THP-1 cells were cultured in RPMI-1640 medium (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland) supplemented with 10 % heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland), 1 % L-glutamine (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland), and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland).

THP-1 cells were incubated with 100 ng/mL phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland) for 24 h to differentiate into macrophage-like THP-1 cells. After differentiation, the macrophage-like THP-1 cells adhered to the flask, and the suspended undifferentiated cells were washed off. The attached macrophage-like THP-1 cells were then incubated with 100 ng/mL LPS (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland) and 20 ng/mL IFN- γ (Peprotech, London, UK) for an additional 24 h to induce M1 macrophage differentiation. The model was described in our previous study [8].

2.4. Mouse primary lymphocyte isolation and culture

This study used 6 Balb/C mice, evenly distributed between sexes (3 females and 3 males). All procedures were approved by the Animals Care Research Ethics Committee of the University of Galway and conducted under individual authorization licenses from the Health Products Regulatory Authority (HPRA) of Ireland (approval number: AE19125_P113_7030596). All animals were housed and cared for under standard operating procedures of the Animal Facility at the Biomedical Sciences Biological Resources Unit, University of Galway. All mice were purchased from Charles River Laboratories.

Female C57BL/6 mice, aged 10–14 weeks, were euthanized by CO₂ asphyxiation. Cervical and inguinal lymph nodes, as well as spleens, were harvested and placed in ice-cold PBS. Single-cell suspensions of the lymph nodes were prepared by mechanical dissociation using the plunger of a 1 mL syringe in a sterile laminar flow hood. The cells were passed through a 40 μ m strainer and pelleted by centrifugation at 800 g for 5 min. The resulting cell pellets were resuspended in mouse T cell medium (RPMI-1640 supplemented with 10 % FBS, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, 1 % non-essential amino acids, 2 mM L-glutamine, 1 % penicillin/streptomycin, and 50 μ M β -mercaptoethanol).

Single-cell suspensions of splenocytes were prepared by gently

dissociating the spleen using the plunger of a 1 mL syringe in a petri dish within a sterile laminar flow hood. The cells were passed through a 40 µm strainer and pelleted by centrifugation at 800 g for 5 min. The supernatant was then removed, and the cells were resuspended in 2 mL of ACK buffer (Gibco) for 5 min on ice to lyse red blood cells. The reaction was neutralized by adding 10 mL of T cell medium. The suspension was subsequently pelleted by centrifugation at 800 g for 5 min, and the cells were resuspended in fresh mouse T cell medium. A suspension containing 90 % lymphocytes and 10 % splenocytes was used for all T cell assays described in the subsequent sections.

2.5. ApoBD preparation and characterization

ApoBD isolation was optimized based on previous studies [30,31,47]. MSCs were treated with staurosporine (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland) at a concentration of 0.5 µM for 12h to induce apoptosis. The supernatant was then collected and centrifuged at 500 g for 10 min at 4 °C to remove cells and debris. Following this, the supernatant was centrifuged at 3000 g for 30 min at 4 °C, yielding a pellet referred to as the 3000 g ApoBD pellet. This pellet was washed twice with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and subjected to another centrifugation at 3000 g. The conditioned medium supernatant was further centrifuged at 16,000 g for 30 min to obtain the 16,000 g ApoBD pellet,

Fig. 1. Preparation and characterization of large and small apoptotic bodies (L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs). A. Preparation of the two categories of ApoBDs. B-D. Representative size distribution histograms of ApoBDs measured using a Malvern Zetasizer. E. Yields of the two ApoBD categories. F-G. Representative transmission electron microscopy images of ApoBDs. The number of independent experiments is represented by the dots in the corresponding figure. Data are presented as mean ± SD. Comparisons for Fig. 1D and E were conducted using a two-tailed unpaired *t*-test. **: *p* < 0.01.

which was also washed twice with PBS and centrifuged again at 16,000 g. The isolation process is summarized in Fig. 1A. The isolated ApoBDs were suspended in 100 μ L of PBS and stored at -80°C , to be used within three days.

For ApoBD characterization, we chose to analyze CD90, CD73, CD44, CD11b and HLA-DR, because these markers were used in MSC characterization. We also characterized PD-L1 because PD-L1 was found to be highly expressed in IFN- γ -licensed MSCs [29,48,49] and PD-L1 is known for its immunosuppressive effect [50,51]. ApoBDs derived from three different human donor MSCs were suspended in FACS (DPBS supplemented with 1 % FBS and 0.05 % sodium azide) buffer and incubated with related antibodies (details in Supplementary Material Table 1, Biolegend, California, USA) for 30 min. After staining, the sample was centrifuged at 16,000 g for 30 min at 4°C to pellet the stained ApoBDs. The stained pelleted ApoBDs were then resuspended in fresh FACS buffer for analysis using the Northern Lights™ 3000 flow cytometer (Cytek).

The total protein content of ApoBDs was quantified using the Bicinchoninic acid (BCA) assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland) after lysis with RIPA buffer (Pierce™, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland).

The size of ApoBDs was assessed through the Zetasizer Nano ZS90.

Regarding morphology, 10 μ L of samples were fixed in 2 % PFA and incubated on 200 mesh gold formvar carbon-coated electron microscopy grids (Aquilent) for 20 min to facilitate attachment. The samples were then incubated with 1 % glutaraldehyde (Sigma) followed by negative staining with 2 % phosphotungstic acid (Sigma) for 15 s. Morphological analysis was conducted using a Hitachi 7500 electron microscope at a magnification of 50,000 \times for wide-field views and 100,000 \times for detailed morphological assessment, all at an accelerating voltage of 75 kV.

2.6. PBMC/ ApoBDs assay and mouse primary lymphocyte/ ApoBDs assay

PBMCs were stained using the CellTrace™ Violet proliferation kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland) following the manufacturer's protocol. The stained cells were then seeded in 96-well round-bottom plates (Sarstedt) at a concentration of 1×10^5 cells in 100 μ L of complete medium, with or without 1×10^4 human (or mouse) T-Activator CD3/CD28 Dynabeads® (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland).

To assess the impact of ApoBDs on human T cell proliferation, 125 ng, 250 ng, 500 ng, 1000 ng and 2000 ng ApoBDs were incubated with PBMCs, respectively. ApoBDs from three donors and PBMC from three donors were used.

In terms of mouse T cell, the incubation was in the presence or absence of 1×10^4 mouse autologous splenocytes. 125 ng, 500 ng and 2000 ng of ApoBDs were incubated with mouse T cells. ApoBDs from three donors and mouse cells from three donors were used.

After 72 h, the cells were harvested and incubated with anti-human antibodies or anti-mouse antibodies (see Supplementary Material Table 1 for additional details) diluted in FACS buffer. The samples were analyzed using a flow cytometer (Cytek), and the flow cytometry data were processed with FlowJo analysis software version 10 (Tree Star Inc.).

2.7. Macrophage/ApoBDs assay

Human THP-1 cells have been demonstrated to be an effective model for primary human monocytes/macrophages [52]. We utilized THP-1 cell-differentiated macrophages to investigate the effects of ApoBDs on macrophages.

M1 macrophages (1×10^5) were seeded in a 96-well plate along with 125 ng, 250 ng, 500 ng, 1000 ng, and 2000 ng of ApoBDs. After 48 h, the cells were harvested and incubated with anti-human antibodies (see Supplementary Material Table 1 for additional details) diluted in

FACS buffer. ApoBDs from three donors were used in this assay.

2.8. ApoBDs uptake assay

ApoBDs were suspended in PBS and incubated with CellTrace™ CFSE (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland) for 30 min. Following the staining, the sample was centrifuged at 16,000 g for 30 min at 4°C to pellet the stained ApoBDs. The stained ApoBDs were then resuspended in fresh THP-1 cell medium for 5 min at 37°C . The sample was centrifuged again at 16,000 g for 30 min at 4°C to pellet the stained ApoBDs, and any unbound dye was removed. Finally, the CFSE-stained ApoBDs were suspended in fresh THP-1 cell medium.

To assess the phagocytosis of ApoBDs by M1 macrophages, 1×10^5 macrophages were seeded in a 96-well round-bottom plate. After differentiating into the M1 phenotype, the macrophages were incubated with 1000 ng of CFSE-stained ApoBDs for 0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 8 h. The cells were then washed three times with PBS and analyzed using a flow cytometer (Cytek). We confirmed that our washing step effectively removed ApoBDs attached to the cell surface without affecting those internalized by the cells (Supplementary Fig. S1F).

For immunocytochemistry staining, the cells were fixed with 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Dublin, Ireland) for 15 min and permeabilized with 0.1 % Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, Wicklow, Ireland) for 15 min. The permeabilized cells were subsequently stained with DAPI (BioLegend, California, USA) and Flash Phalloidin™ Red 594 (BioLegend, California, USA). Images were captured using an Olympus CKX53 microscope and analyzed with cell-Sens imaging software. ApoBDs from three donors were utilized in this assay.

2.9. Statistical analysis and evaluation

Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Most comparisons between groups were conducted using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Comparisons for Fig. 3A, D, and F, Fig. 4A, D, and G; Fig. 5A and C, Fig. 6A and Fig. 7C and E were performed using two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test. Comparisons for Fig. 1D and E; Fig. 2B; and Supplementary Fig. S1E were conducted using a two-tailed unpaired *t*-test. Differences were considered significant for $p < 0.05$, and *p*-values close to 0.05 were labeled in the figures. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Software (version 8.0.2). The study utilized MSCs from three donors, PBMCs from another three donors, and lymphocytes from four donor mice. Details of the cross-co-culture procedure are provided in Supplementary Material Table 2.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of human MSCs

MSCs from three healthy donors were used in this study. Flow cytometry was used to identify protein expression on the cell surface of MSCs (CD90, CD73, CD44, CD11b, CD45 and HLA-DR). In brief, MSCs were positive in CD90, CD73 and CD44 and low in CD45, CD11b and HLA-DR. The differentiation capacity (adipogenic and osteogenic) of MSCs from all three donors was verified. These results can be found in our previous research publications [8,29].

3.2. Characterization of human MSC-derived ApoBDs

As shown in Fig. 1A, 3000 g pellet was collected as the 3000 g ApoBDs and following that the 16,000 g pellet was collected as the 16,000 g ApoBDs. As shown in Fig. 1B-D, the pellet from three donors was measured by the Malvern Zeta Potential Analyzer for their sizes. We found these two batches of ApoBDs were distinct in size. The 3000 g pellet was 723 ± 10.1 nm, and the 16,000 g was 535.6 ± 43.2 nm. The

Fig. 2. Flow cytometric characterization of apoptotic bodies (ApoBDs). **A.** Gating strategy for identifying ApoBDs (FMO: fluorescence minus one). **B.** Median forward scatter (FSC) values of ApoBDs. **C.** Expression levels of selected proteins on ApoBDs. Both large and small ApoBDs derived from mesenchymal stromal cells exhibited high expression levels of CD90, CD73, and CD44, while showing low expression of CD11b, HLA-DR, and PD-L1. The number of independent experiments is represented by the dots in the corresponding figure. Data are presented as mean \pm SD, and analyzed using a two-tailed unpaired t-test. *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$.

3000 g pellet ApoBDs pellet was significantly larger than the 16,000 g ApoBDs pellet. In the subsequent experiments, the 3000 g pellet was defined as the large ApoBDs (L-ApoBDs) and the 16,000 g pellet was defined as the small ApoBDs (S-ApoBDs). Visualized and confirmed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (Fig. 1F-G), L-ApoBDs were larger than S-ApoBDs. Both ApoBDs had bilayer membrane structure, which is consistent with the guideline published by ISEV [41].

We also quantified the yield of both ApoBDs as shown in Fig. 1E, with the yield of S-ApoBDs being higher compared to L-ApoBDs. The yield of S-ApoBDs was 26.9 ± 3.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{million MSCs}$ and the L-ApoBDs was 16.8 ± 4.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{million MSCs}$.

Both ApoBDs were injected into the flow cytometer for further characterization. As shown in Fig. 2A, we gated the annexin-V positive subpopulation to get the ApoBDs. The forward scatters (FSC) of both ApoBDs were compared in Fig. 2A-B. The FSC of L-ApoBDs was larger than S-ApoBDs and the p -value was 0.0685 (near significance). Because the FSC reflects the size of the injected particle, this FSC data was consistent with the data measured by the Malvern Zeta Potential Analyzer.

Utilizing the gating strategy shown in Fig. 2A, the surface marker profile of both ApoBDs was characterized (Fig. 2C). We investigated the commonly seen markers of MSC in MSC-derived ApoBDs. Both ApoBDs stained positive for the same selected surface proteins: they expressed CD90, CD73 and CD44 highly and they expressed CD11b, HLA-DR and PD-L1 lowly. These expression profiles were also consistent with their parental MSCs [29].

3.3. ApoBDs/human PBMCs assay

The effects of both ApoBDs on allogeneic PBMCs were first investigated because the allogeneic T cell proliferation assay is regarded as the gold standard for validation of immunomodulation. We incubated PBMCs with gradient concentrations of both ApoBDs to study the dosage dependence. The gating strategy was shown in Supplementary Fig. S1A. As displayed in Fig. 3A, with the concentration of both ApoBDs increased, the frequency of proliferated CD3⁺, CD3⁺/CD4⁺ and CD3⁺/CD8⁺ T cells decreased. This demonstrated both ApoBDs can inhibit allogeneic T cell proliferation. We found L-ApoBDs were stronger in this inhibitory effect on CD3⁺ and CD3⁺/CD4⁺ T cells, with p -values of 0.0767 and 0.0037 respectively. As displayed in Fig. 3B, the stimulated control group and the highest dosage ApoBD groups were compared to investigate whether there is any significance between the control and the experimental groups. In terms of the highest dosage, both ApoBDs inhibited T cell proliferation significantly. Besides, L-ApoBDs were significantly stronger in inhibiting CD3⁺/CD4⁺ and CD3⁺/CD8⁺ T cell proliferation. In terms of CD3⁺/CD8⁺ T cell proliferation, we observed a difference in Fig. 3B, but not in Fig. 3A. This discrepancy is due to differences in the statistical analyses. Fig. 3A compares four dosages of large apoptotic bodies with those of small apoptotic bodies, while Fig. 3B focuses solely on the highest dosage. This indicates that, in inhibiting CD8 T cell proliferation, the effects are similar at lower dosages but diverge at the highest dosages.

We also visualized the proliferated Celltrace Violet fluorescence as displayed in Fig. 3C. An additional generation of proliferating T cells can be observed in the stimulated control group compared to the experimental group. At last, the viability of PBMCs was quantified because

Fig. 3. ApoBDs/human PBMCs assay: both L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs inhibit allogenic T cell proliferation without exhibiting toxicity to PBMCs. PBMCs were stimulated with anti-CD3/CD28 beads and harvested after 72 h of incubation. **A.** Percentage of proliferating CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. **B.** Percentage of proliferating CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. **C.** Representative CellTrace Violet (CTV) histograms of CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. **D.** Lymphocyte viability following treatment with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. **E.** Lymphocyte viability following treatment with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. **F.** Viability of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. **G.** Viability of PBMCs treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. PBMCs represent all the cells detected in the flow cytometry analysis, with the lymphocyte gate illustrated in Supplementary Fig. S1A. The stimulated control group refers to cells that were activated using anti-CD3/CD28 beads to promote lymphocyte expansion. In contrast, the unstimulated control group did not receive bead stimulation, and its data, presented in Supplementary Material Figure, served as a reference for gating the proliferated subpopulation. The L-ApoBD and S-ApoBD groups consisted of stimulated cells that were subsequently treated with their respective ApoBD preparations. All results are derived from three independent experiments and quantified by flow cytometry. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Data in panels A, D, and F were analyzed using two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test, while panels B, E, and G were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test. ns: not significant; *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$. (L-ApoBDs: large apoptotic bodies; s-ApoBDs: small apoptotic bodies). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

some previous studies reported the cytotoxicity of staurosporine [53,54].

We wanted to demonstrate that both ApoBDs were non-cytotoxic because during the preparation, the pellet was washed at least two times to remove any possible trace of water-soluble staurosporine. As displayed in Fig. 3D-E, both ApoBDs were considered non-cytotoxic to the human primary lymphocytes. The results are similar with PBMCs as displayed in Fig. 3F-G. In terms of the PBMCs, the viability was ~70 % while the lymphocytes' viability was ~86 %. T cell expansion beads resulted in a high frequency of expanded viable T lymphocytes.

3.4. ApoBDs/macrophages assay

Next, we investigated whether both ApoBDs can polarize M1 macrophages. Human THP-1 differentiated M1 macrophages were incubated with the gradient concentration of both ApoBDs. The gating strategy was shown in Supplementary Fig. S1B. As shown in Fig. 4A and D, increasing the dosage of both ApoBDs led to an upregulation in CD163 and CD206 expression, suggesting that both ApoBDs have the potential to polarize M1 macrophages toward the M2 phenotype. In Fig. 4A, at a dosage of 2000 ng, L-ApoBDs exhibited a stronger effect in upregulating CD163 expression compared to S-ApoBDs, with a *p*-value of 0.0628. Furthermore, when comparing the expression profiles of M1 macrophage controls and ApoBD-treated groups (Fig. 4B and E), 2000 ng of L-ApoBDs significantly increased CD163 expression (*P* = 0.0568), whereas S-ApoBDs did not induce a significant upregulation (*P* > 0.05). However, regarding CD206 expression, neither ApoBD induced a statistically significant increase, despite a clear dose-dependent trend observed in the data (Fig. 4D). Next, the fluorescence histograms of CD163 and CD206 quantified by flow cytometer were visualized in Fig. 4C and F. Overall, we found that L-ApoBDs upregulated CD163, while S-ApoBDs also increased CD163 expression, albeit without statistical significance. Regarding CD206 expression, although its expression was elevated, the increase induced by ApoBDs was not statistically significant.

Moreover, we also investigated the viability of macrophages to both ApoBDs. As displayed in Fig. 4G-H, both ApoBDs preparations had no effects on macrophage viability, which further demonstrated that both ApoBDs are non-cytotoxic.

3.5. ApoBDs/mouse primary lymphocytes assay

Next, we studied the effects of human ApoBDs on mouse primary lymphocytes in preparation for our future in vivo mouse assay of human MSC-derived apoptotic bodies. We previously found that interspecies incompatibilities limit the immunomodulatory effects of human mesenchymal stromal cells in rats [55]. Therefore, we included an ex vivo assay using primary mouse T lymphocytes to investigate whether human MSC-derived apoptotic bodies affect mouse cells.

At first, two deep cervical, two superficial cervical and two inguinal lymph nodes were harvested. We studied two incubation models, one in the presence and one in the absence of autologous splenocytes because splenocytes were rich in antigen-presenting cells which may mediate a more potent immunological reaction. The gating strategy of the mouse primary lymphocytes was shown in the Supplementary Fig. S1C.

As shown in Fig. 5A, in the presence of the splenocytes, with the increasing dosage of both ApoBDs, the frequency of proliferated CD3+ and CD3+/CD4+ T cells decreased. This indicated that both ApoBDs can inhibit the proliferation of CD3+ and CD3+/CD4+ T cells. However, the frequency of proliferated CD3+/CD8+ did not significantly change. When comparing L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs, L-ApoBDs were significantly more potent than S-ApoBDs in inhibiting the proliferation of murine CD3+ and CD3+/CD4+ T cells. However, both ApoBDs affected limitedly on CD3+/CD8+ T cells. In terms of the high dosage, as shown in Fig. 5B, both ApoBDs significantly inhibited the proliferation of murine CD3+ and CD3+/CD4+ T cells when compared with the stimulated control group. The two subtypes of ApoBDs had statistically the same

efficiency. Both high dosages of ApoBDs affected limitedly on CD3+/CD8+ T cells.

In the absence of splenocytes, similarly, with the increasing dosage of both ApoBDs, the frequency of proliferated CD3+, CD3+/CD4+ and CD3+/CD8+ T cells decreased. However, the inhibitory effects led by both ApoBDs did not have significant statistical differences with each other as shown in Fig. 5C. In Fig. 5D, we compared the frequency of proliferated T cells in the stimulated control group and high dose of ApoBDs-treated groups. In the results, both 2000 ng of L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs inhibited the proliferation of mouse CD3+, CD3+/CD4+ and CD3+/CD8+ T cells. These inhibitory effects led by L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs were statistically similar with each other.

We finally tested the potential toxicity of both ApoBDs on mouse primary lymphocytes. As displayed in Fig. 5A, with the dosage increasing, both ApoBDs reduced the viability of mouse lymphocytes in the absence of splenocytes, however, in the presence of splenocytes, both ApoBDs did not affect the viability of the mouse lymphocytes. Despite the effects of both ApoBDs on splenocytes none of them were statistically significant. When compared to the viability resulting from the highest dosage of the ApoBDs, as shown in Fig. 6B, the ApoBDs did not lower the viability of mouse lymphocytes statistically whether with or without the splenocytes.

In all, human MSC-derived L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs can inhibit the proliferation of the murine primary lymphocytes with or without the addition of autologous splenocytes. The L-ApoBDs were more potent to inhibit the proliferation of mouse CD3+ and CD3+/CD4+ T cells, in the absence of splenocytes. And as for high dosage or without splenocytes, both ApoBDs worked similarly in inhibiting murine T cell proliferation. We conclude that, both ApoBDs were non-cytotoxic to the murine primary lymphocytes.

3.6. ApoBDs/macrophage uptake assay

Our previous study proved that ApoBDs were primarily taken up by CD14+ monocytes in PBMC. And THP-1 differentiated macrophages are an excellent model for studying the uptake of ApoBDs [29]. In the present study, we also utilized the THP-1 differentiated macrophage model to study the uptake difference between L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs. 1000 ng of both CFSE-labeled ApoBDs were incubated with 1×10^5 macrophages. The pictures were taken by fluorescence microscopy at 0, 0.5 h, 1 h, 2 h, 4 h and 8 h. After an 8-h incubation, as shown in Fig. 7A, the ApoBDs were stained in green CFSE the macrophagic nuclei were stained in blue DAPI and the macrophagic cytoskeleton was stained in red phalloidin. In the 400× magnification field of view, internalized ApoBDs were observed (indicated by the arrows). Next, we studied the dynamic fluorescent intensity of the internalized ApoBDs according to pictures as shown representatively in Fig. 7B. The results were shown in Fig. 7C: the L-ApoBDs were rapidly and very significantly taken up by macrophages. Finally, to pursue an accurate fluorescent value, the macrophages, after incubation with the stained ApoBDs, were injected into the flow cytometer. The histograms were visualized as Fig. 7D. The fluorescent values are shown in Fig. 7E: As already demonstrated by fluorescence microscopy, the L-ApoBDs were rapidly and very significantly taken up by macrophages. Both assays showed rapid and significant uptake of ApoBDs.

Since L-ApoBDs are larger than S-ApoBDs, they may appear brighter due to their greater volume, which allows them to bind more fluorescent dye. Consequently, this could lead to a higher CFSE median fluorescence intensity (MFI) in macrophages after co-incubation. To minimize potential bias, we stained both L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs with CFSE and quantified their MFI. As shown in Supplementary Fig. S1D and E, L-ApoBDs appeared darker than S-ApoBDs following CFSE staining. We speculate that this may be due to the higher surface-to-volume ratio of S-ApoBDs, which could enhance their ability to incorporate or retain CFSE per unit volume compared to their larger counterparts. Since CFSE labeling primarily depends on surface area, the relatively greater surface

Fig. 4. The apoptotic bodies (ApoBDs)/macrophage assay. Both L-ApoBDs and S-ApoBDs can polarize THP-1-differentiated M1 macrophages to an M2 phenotype, and they are non-cytotoxic to THP-1-differentiated macrophages. A. CD163 expression in macrophages treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. B. CD163 expression in macrophages treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. C. Representative histogram of CD163 expression in macrophages treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. D. CD206 expression in macrophages treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. E. CD206 expression in macrophages treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. F. Representative histogram of CD206 expression in macrophages treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. G. Macrophage viability following treatment with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. H. Macrophage viability following treatment with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. The incubation period was 48 h. All results represent three independent experiments and quantified by flow cytometry. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Data in panels A, D, and G were analyzed using two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test, while panels B, E, and H were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test. ns: not significant. (L-ApoBDs: large apoptotic bodies; S-ApoBDs: small apoptotic bodies).

Fig. 5. The apoptotic bodies (ApoBDs)/mouse primary immunocytes assay. Both large and small ApoBDs inhibit the proliferation of mouse T cells. Mouse primary lymphocytes were stimulated with anti-CD3/CD28 beads and harvested after 72 h of incubation. **A.** The percentage of proliferated CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations, in the presence of autologous splenocytes. **B.** The percentage of proliferated CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs, in the presence of autologous splenocytes. **C.** The percentage of proliferated CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations, in the absence of splenocytes. **D.** The percentage of proliferated CD3+, CD3+/CD4+, and CD3+/CD8+ T cells treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs, in the absence of splenocytes. The stimulated control group refers to cells that were activated using anti-CD3/CD28 beads to promote lymphocyte expansion. In contrast, the unstimulated control group did not receive bead stimulation, and its data, presented in Supplementary Material Figure, served as a reference for gating the proliferated subpopulation. The L-ApoBD and S-ApoBD groups consisted of stimulated cells that were subsequently treated with their respective ApoBD preparations. All results represent three independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Data in panels A and C were analyzed using two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test, while panels B and D were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test. ns: not significant; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. (L-ApoBDs: large apoptotic bodies; S-ApoBDs: small apoptotic bodies).

Fig. 6. Viability of mouse primary lymphocytes assay. Both large and small ApoBDs were non-cytotoxic to primary mouse lymphocytes. A. Viability of mouse primary lymphocytes (\pm autologous splenocytes) treated with ApoBDs at varying concentrations. B. Viability of mouse primary lymphocytes (\pm autologous splenocytes) treated with 2000 ng of ApoBDs. All results are from three independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Panel A was analyzed using two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test, and panel B was analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test. ns: not significant. (L-ApoBDs: large apoptotic bodies; S-ApoBDs: small apoptotic bodies).

area of smaller vesicles may facilitate increased dye accumulation. However, macrophages that internalized L-ApoBDs exhibited higher fluorescence than those internalizing S-ApoBDs (Fig. 7C and E), confirming that L-ApoBDs were more rapidly and efficiently taken up by macrophages.

4. Discussion

In the present study, we isolated and extensively characterized two subpopulations of human bone marrow MSC-derived ApoBDs. Both ApoBDs expressed similar protein markers as their parental cells but they were distinct in size. Both ApoBDs can polarize human M1 macrophage to M2 phenotype and inhibit allogeneic T cell and mouse primary lymphocyte proliferation. Interestingly, we found L-ApoBDs were stronger than S-ApoBDs in immunomodulation such as inhibiting allogeneic CD3⁺/CD4⁺ and CD3⁺/CD8⁺ T cell proliferation, upregulating M2 macrophagic CD163 expression and inhibiting mouse CD3⁺ and CD3⁺/CD4⁺ T cell proliferation (in the absence of splenocytes). Also, L-ApoBDs can be phagocytosed by macrophages more rapidly compared to S-ApoBDs. At last, both ApoBDs were deemed non-cytotoxic due to minimal effects on the viability of the recipient cells. This study evaluates the two primary centrifugation conditions for ApoBDs, which may help establish a standardized ApoBD isolation protocol in the future. Additionally, we characterized ApoBDs using multiple techniques, enhancing our understanding of their properties.

Finally, we verified the in vitro immunomodulatory capacity of ApoBDs, highlighting their potential in MSC-based therapy.

Compared to small EVs, the authors chose to study ApoBDs because: 1) MSCs were verified undergoing apoptosis after in-vivo infusion and apoptotic MSC would release ApoBDs [25]; 2) MSC apoptosis was required for their therapeutic function including immunomodulation [25]; 3) ApoBDs were shown to have the same therapeutic effects as their parental non-apoptotic cells [20–23] and 4) MSC-derived ApoBDs were described as anti-inflammatory in many models [29–31]. In summary, our findings confirm that MSC-derived apoptotic bodies, like MSC-derived small EVs [56,57], hold potential for immunomodulatory therapy. However, this study did not include in vivo research. To further advance this therapeutic immunomodulatory approach, additional studies are needed to investigate in vivo processes such as absorption, biodistribution, and metabolism of MSC-derived apoptotic bodies.

In the present study, we found L-ApoBDs were stronger than S-ApoBDs in immunomodulation such as inhibiting allogeneic CD3⁺/CD4⁺ and CD3⁺/CD8⁺ T cell proliferation, upregulating M2 macrophagic CD163 expression and inhibiting mouse CD3⁺ and CD3⁺/CD4⁺ T cell proliferation. We concluded that L-ApoBDs exhibit stronger immunomodulatory effects than S-ApoBDs. We propose three potential mechanisms underlying this enhanced effect, which also represent key directions for future research on ApoBDs. (1) Surface Area and Ligand Density: L-ApoBDs possess a larger surface area, which may facilitate more efficient interactions with immune cells. Key immunomodulatory

Fig. 7. ApoBDs/macrophage uptake assay. **A.** Immunocytochemistry staining of macrophages incubated with CFSE-stained ApoBDs for 8 h. **B.** Immunocytochemistry images of macrophages at multiple time points during incubation. **C.** Internalized green fluorescence intensity of macrophages at each time point, by immunocytochemistry. **D.** Representative histogram of CFSE fluorescence intensity in macrophages at each time point, by flow cytometry. **E.** Median fluorescence intensity (MFI) of CFSE in macrophages at each time point, quantified by flow cytometry. All results represent three independent experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Data in panels C and E were analyzed using two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test. *** $p < 0.001$. (L-ApoBDs: large apoptotic bodies; S-ApoBDs: small apoptotic bodies). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

molecules, such as phosphatidylserine (PS) and damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), are likely to be more exposed, thereby enhancing receptor engagement. (2) Cargo Packaging and Release: The composition and structural organization of bioactive cargo—including proteins, cytokines, miRNAs, and lipids—may vary with ApoBD size. L-ApoBDs may have a distinct lipid composition or vesicular architecture that promotes more efficient cargo release or uptake by immune cells. Future omics studies will be instrumental in elucidating these differences. (3) Differential Uptake by Immune Cells: The efficiency of phagocytosis and endocytosis is influenced by particle size. L-ApoBDs may be preferentially internalized by antigen-presenting cells, such as dendritic cells and macrophages, leading to more potent downstream immunomodulatory effects. The primary experimental evidence supporting this hypothesis is presented in this study.

The in-vitro cytotoxicity of staurosporine-generated ApoBDs was investigated and demonstrated in this study because there is a concern about the use of staurosporine as an ApoBD-inducing agent. Staurosporine is an anti-cancer drug [53,54] and its release from ApoBDs

could have a negative effect when these ApoBDs are considered for immunomodulatory therapy. Some researchers utilized ultra-violet (UV) light instead to induce apoptosis [58], in order to prevent the influence of staurosporine. However, the apoptosis-inducing efficiency of UV light varies, so the apoptotic cell frequency was not as stable as with the staurosporine-induced. In all, we verified that staurosporine is not toxic to both human and mouse T cells and macrophages and is a non-cytotoxic and highly efficient agent for preparing ApoBDs.

In our previous study [29], we isolated ApoBDs from cytokine-licensed MSCs but did not observe a significant effect of cytokines on the ApoBDs. Due to cost considerations, we continued to focus on ApoBDs derived from naïve MSCs. Additionally, we found that the size distribution of the ApoBDs was not highly concentrated after only 16,000 g centrifugation in our previous study. This led us to explore whether large ApoBDs could be isolated first, followed by the smaller ones. In the future, more precise centrifugation conditions could be developed to improve isolation.

The present study employed multiple T cell proliferation assays, as

this is currently the gold standard for verifying in vitro immunomodulatory capacity. For mouse T cell proliferation, we used two models—one with and one without autologous splenocytes—because we found that splenocytes play a crucial role in antigen presentation [59,60] and may influence T cell proliferation. Ultimately, we observed that ApoBDs were effective to inhibit mouse T cell proliferation regardless of the presence or absence of splenocytes.

We used THP-1 cells as a macrophage model instead of isolating monocytes from blood or mouse lymph nodes, as monocytes comprise only a small fraction of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) (10–20 % [61]) and an even smaller percentage (1–5 %) in mouse lymph nodes. Additionally, the available PBMCs and mouse tissues were prioritized for the more critical T cell proliferation assays, and the study had limited samples for additional monocyte isolation. Additionally, THP-1-differentiated macrophages have been widely studied and are commonly used as a substitute for primary macrophages [52,62]. Moreover, the differentiation time from THP-1 cells to macrophages (~1 day) [8,29] is shorter than the time required to differentiate monocytes into macrophages (5–7 days) [63,64], which is more convenient.

5. Conclusion

The study evaluated and characterized two subpopulations of apoptotic bodies derived from human bone marrow mesenchymal stromal cells. The results indicated that large apoptotic bodies exhibit superior immunomodulatory effects compared to small apoptotic bodies. These effects include stronger inhibition of T-cell proliferation in both human and murine models, enhanced upregulation of markers associated with M2 macrophage polarization, and faster phagocytosis by macrophages. Both subpopulations of apoptotic bodies were confirmed to be non-cytotoxic, suggesting their potential utility in mesenchymal stromal cell-based therapeutic applications. The findings underscore the importance of developing standardized isolation protocols, emphasizing the role of size-specific apoptotic bodies in optimizing therapeutic efficacy. However, further in vivo studies are needed to investigate the biodistribution, absorption, and metabolism of these apoptotic bodies.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jiemin Wang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Syedmohammad Moosavizadeh:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Manon Jammes:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Abbas Tabasi:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Trung Bach:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Aideen E. Ryan:** Writing

– review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Thomas Ritter:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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